

Table continued

Tested rice		Growth period (d)	Dry straw wt (kg/plot)	Av panicles/plant	Grains/panicle	Ripe state	Filled spikelets (%)	Grain yield (kg/plot)	Grain yield rank
Variety	Type ^a								
IR36	IV	134	1.50	10.5	62.6	GWFR	8.1	0.71	13
V-you 35	HV	133	1.75	10.4	59.6	GWFR	25.7	0.67	14
IR42	IV	143	3.17	8.2	103.6	GWFR	25.0	0.58	15
Wanhuaai 1	RV	141	2.00	7.7	81.0	GWFR	43.7	0.53	16
Shanyou 64	HV	132	2.66	10.3	63.5	GWFR	7.7	0.51	17
Xiangzaizao 9	RV	134	1.52	14.5	40.2	GWFR	14.4	0.45	18
Shanyou 36	HV	131	2.62	11.1	59.4	GWFR	4.2	0.35	19
Guo 16	RV	138	2.41	9.8	104.0	GWFR	16.0	0.33	20
Shanyou 63	HV	133	2.41	9.7	75.5	GWFR	11.7	0.31	21
Yuachi 231-8	RV	136	2.57	15.0	56.6	GWFR	0.5	0.24	22
IR131427-60-1-3-2-2	IV	132	2.71	13.0	57.2	GWFR	2.1	0.21	23
IR50	IV	132	2.96	14.6	60.5	GWFR	7.4	0.19	24
Liuyou 2	HV	133	2.86	7.8	60.1	GWFR	16.0	0.19	24
Ce 64	RV	133	2.87	8.7	87.6	GWFR	12.9	0.18	25
IR58	IV	132	2.58	8.1	79.3	GWFR	0.4	0.14	26
IR29725-22-3-3-3	IV	132	2.67	11.0	57.0	GWFR	2.5	0.08	27
IR9764-45-2-2	IV	145	---	---	---	GWFR	---	---	---
IR13145-45-2-3	IV	145	---	---	---	GWFR	---	---	---
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	IV	145	---	---	---	GWFR	---	---	---

^aIV = IRRI variety. ^b Green without full ripeness.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Early-maturing hybrid rice combinations

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Ten newly developed early-maturing hybrid rice combinations were tested in a six-location yield trial in the first cropping season 1986 in Hunan Province. Plot size was 13.3 m² in 3 replications. Sowing was from the end of Mar to early Apr with harvesting

date by the end of Jul.

Wei You 35 is a high-yielding combination developed in 1980. Xie Qing Zao A/Xuan 10-19 had the significantly highest yield (see table). It is moderately resistant to bacterial blight and blast. L301 A/R29, with good grain quality, was selected in Texas, USA, by Chinese scientists. Its yield is not significantly lower than that of Wei You 35. Xie Qing Zao A/Xuan 10-19 and L301 A/R29 were developed by the Hunan Hybrid Rice Research Center. □

Morphological characters, seed setting, and dry matter production of A and B lines

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Morphological characters, seed set percentage, root to straw ratio, and dry matter production were estimated in 11 cytotsterile lines of rice (A) and their maintainers (B). Five are from China, four from IRRI, and two from TNAU.

The cytotsteriles were high in total dry matter production, predominantly distributed in root and straw (see table). In general, root:straw was higher in A lines than in B lines. Plants of B lines were taller, but panicle length was greater in A lines.

The increased weight of vegetative parts in A lines may be due to the mobilization of nutrients to tillers and the prolonged vegetative phase. These, however, were not utilized by the reproductive parts because of poor sink

Growth duration and yield of newly developed early-maturing rice hybrids. Hunan, China, 1986.

Combination	Growth duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check	Yield/d per ha (kg)
Xie Qing Zao A/Xuan 10-19	118.8	7.9	7.66 ^a	66.8
L301 A/R29	117.4	7.2	-2.37	61.4
Xie Qing Zao A/S ₅ -200	119.6	7.0	-4.44	59.0
V ₂₀ A/H 78	121.6	7.0	-5.17	57.6
Wei You 26	117.0	6.8	-7.76*	58.1
V ₂₀ A/383	117.8	6.8	-7.90*	51.8
Z 97 A/To 326	118.8	6.8	-8.14*	57.0
V ₂₀ A/305	119.0	6.7	-9.69*	56.0
V ₂₀ A/S ₅ -990	115.0	6.5	-11.57**	56.7
Chang 22 A/T 65	126.6	5.5	-24.85**	43.8
Wei You 35 (check)	120.6	7.4		61.2

^a Significant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Characters of A and B lines. TNAU, India.

Line	Plant ht (cm)		Panicle length (cm)		Panicle exertion ^a (cm) B	Tillers (no.)		Root length (cm)		Straw dry wt (g)		Root dry wt (g)		Root to straw ratio		Grain setting (%)	
	A	B	A	B		A	B	A	B	A	A	B	B	A	B	A	B
V20	64	66	19.9	18.0	1.52	8	6	13.6	12.2	5.8	4.1	4.7	2.5	1.23	1.64	19.5	80.9
Zhen-shan 97	57	73	20.8	19.6	1.54	19	6	18.6	17.2	12.5	4.3	6.0	2.5	2.08	1.72	13.5	79.8
Er-jiu-Nan 1	63	65	18.8	17.3	1.64	20	8	18.0	17.0	14.5	4.5	8.5	3.0	1.71	1.50	11.0	88.6
Yar-ai-Zhao 1	67	68	18.5	19.3	1.66	17	9	14.0	14.8	8.5	7.5	7.5	5.0	1.13	1.50	16.2	68.5
Yar-ai-Zhao 2	70	78	22.5	21.2	1.68	15	6	10.6	11.6	8.3	6.1	5.5	4.7	1.51	1.30	9.6	74.7
IR46827	62	69	19.9	17.9	1.61	24	18	17.8	19.3	17.8	5.0	8.5	3.5	2.09	1.43	14.3	77.2
IR46828	62	74	22.1	19.8	1.62	19	13	17.7	15.1	17.5	5.2	7.0	3.3	2.50	1.56	7.5	77.9
IR46829	58	67	20.0	18.1	1.58	11	7	14.5	16.3	16.5	4.8	6.0	4.0	2.75	1.20	11.5	81.8
IR46830	58	63	21.4	18.5	1.60	21	8	18.2	17.1	15.3	4.6	7.7	4.0	1.99	1.15	17.6	76.6
TNMS31	90	96	22.0	21.5	1.65	17	10	14.7	14.2	16.6	11.5	9.2	8.5	1.80	1.35	9.5	85.9
TNMS37	82	93	22.1	22.9	1.74	15	9	18.9	17.2	18.3	9.0	8.0	6.5	2.29	1.38	17.9	87.9
Mean	67	74	20.7	19.5	1.62	17	9	16.1	15.6	13.8	6.1	7.2	4.3	1.92	1.43	13.5	80.0
CD (0.05)	16	21	2.3	2.6	ns	6	5	3.2	2.5	5.2	2.6	2.1	1.8	0.48	ns	3.4	12.4

^aValues were zero for A.

size reflected by spikelet sterility. The reduction in height of A lines may be due to lack of panicle exertion from the

boot leaf. Poor panicle exertion in the male sterile lines may be associated with a nonrestorer gene or it may be due to

interaction between nonrestorer gene and sterile cytoplasm. □

Performance of three new hybrid rices

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We evaluated the yield potential and grain quality of three new hybrid rices in Changsha in May-Sep 1986. Seeds were sown 14 May; 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 2 seedlings/hill and 20 × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications.

II-32 A/MH63 performed well and is expected to be released commercially (see table). Although its yield was not significantly higher than that of Shan You 63, a widely grown hybrid in south and southwest China, its seed production is considerably higher because the cytoplasmic male sterile (cms) line II-32 A possesses such floral traits as large stigma, good panicle, and stigma exertion, suitable for a higher natural outcrossing rate.

The cms lines used in the new hybrids possess a cms system different from that of WA types. Tian-Ai A is gametophytic, others are sporophytic. MH63, the R line used in the four combinations, was derived from a strain of Gui 630/IR30.

Lodging caused some yield loss due to heavy rain during grain ripening. □

Performance of new hybrid rices in yield trials in Changsha, China, 1986.

Character	11-32 A/ MH63	Tian Ai A/ MH63	Guang-Tan 69 A/ MH63	Shan You 63 (check)
Plant height (cm)	119	119	123	117
Growth duration (d)	137	132	133	129
Panicles (no./m ²)	296	342	320	311
Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	122	93	97	106
1000-grain wt (g)	27.2	27.6	25.5	29.3
Yield (t/ha)	8.5	7.8	7.4	8.3
Brown rice yield (%)	79.7	78.7	80.4	
length (mm)	6.5	6.7	6.6	
width (%)	2.6	2.5	2.4	
length: width	2.5	2.7	2.8	
Total milling yield (%)	75.7	72.7	73.8	
Head rice (%)	33.6	62.5	41.0	
Chalky rice ^a (%)	15.5	32.0	27.0	
Chalky area of milled rice ^a (%)	1.8	2.3	4.3	
Gel consistency (mm)	27	35	38.5	
Alkali spreading value (scale)	6.7	5.6	6.5	
Amylose content (%)	20.3	21.2	21.1	

^aBased on the weight of rough rice.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

A simple device for mass extraction of rice anthers

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Anther culture techniques for use in breeding generally show low efficiency.

Inoculating several thousand anthers is necessary to generate a pollen-plants population large enough for selecting desirable type(s). Because their flowering duration is short, several F₁ hybrids or other material may have to be utilized within a short period. Isolation of anthers becomes a cumbersome and labor-intensive job.